

MODERN FORMS OF ORGANIZING STUDENTS INDEPENDENT WORK AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7674742>

Abstract. *This article talks about the organization of independent education in higher education institutions. Today, proper organization of independent education is an urgent issue. Therefore, in this article, we will try to reveal the pedagogical problems of modern forms used in the organization of students' independent work and ways to solve them.*

Keywords: *independent education, credit module, independent thinking, organization, creative thinking.*

There is no doubt that every change in the field of education will have a positive effect on the development of our society. Increasing the intellectual potential of the country is considered an important factor in the preparation of mature, competitive personnel who can meet the requirements of the state education standard. Striving to independently acquire knowledge in any field is the most distinctive feature of student activity in an educational institution, the basis of independent study and knowledge acquisition. Independent knowledge acquisition and control in the educational system is one of the main factors of independent education. In getting independent education, first of all, it is necessary to form in students the need for independent work, free, creative activity and, most importantly, independent thinking.

Chapter 3 of the Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 entitled "Strategic Goals and Priority Areas of the Development of the Higher Education System" § 1 entitled "Expanding the scope of higher education, improving the quality of training of highly educated specialists" [1, 5] "Increasing the share of independent study hours, students' independent education, critical and creative thinking, systematic analysis, formation of entrepreneurial skills, introduction of methods and technologies aimed at strengthening competencies in the educational process, directing the educational process to the formation of practical skills, international education in this regard "wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and educational materials based on the standards" [1, 7], independent education of learners, continuous improvement of independent work skills, necessary for specialists special attention is paid to the development of competencies, creativity, research, and logical thinking.

A student's independent work is a systematic activity aimed at mastering a certain part of the knowledge, skills and qualifications specified in the curriculum of a particular subject by the student based on the advice and recommendations of the subject teacher outside the auditorium and auditorium.

"According to the requirements of the present time, the educational process is not only to provide students with knowledge, to develop their thinking ability, to form learning skills for using the acquired knowledge, but also to help them search for independent knowledge, consists in teaching the forms, methods, and means of mastering" [6, 4].

"Increasing students' independent knowledge, extracting what is needed from the flow of information and forming the ability to process and analyze data is considered one of the main directions of the process of training quality personnel [2, 4]"

"Organization of student's independent work in the initial stages of education is connected with a number of tasks. It is especially difficult for first-year students to get used to the different requirements of higher education. Because they hardly know how to organize their independent activities during the education process" [3, 4].

"It is a big problem for them to find information from which source and how to summarize it, to clearly and vividly express their opinion, to properly allocate their time, as well as to correctly assess their mental and physical capabilities. . The main thing is that they are not mentally ready for independent education" [3, 6].

Therefore, every professor-teacher should first instill confidence in the student in his abilities and mental capabilities, patiently and step by step teach them to properly organize independent learning. . It is necessary to increase their initiative and role, taking into account the fact that the knowledge and skills acquired independently by students become more complicated and expanded from course to course. Then, the student who has started independent education can not only do the work assigned by the teacher, but also independently choose and master the additional knowledge that he considers necessary, depending on his needs, interests and abilities.

Independent education is organized in the following forms:

1. Independent mastering of subjects with the help of regulatory legal documents and educational literature;
2. Preparing abstracts on topics;
3. Preparing for seminars and practical training;
4. Preparation of scientific articles and theses;
5. Preparation of projects covering current problems of science;
6. Application of theoretical knowledge in practice;
6. Finding solutions to existing problems in practice;
7. Writing annotations to the main scientific literature on the studied topic, etc.

The student's independent work is an integral part of the study hour specified in the curriculum for mastering a specific subject, and it is provided with methodological information resources.

Independent education at the university can be carried out in the form of an abstract, homework, presentation, various cases, assignments and other similar forms, depending on the characteristics of each subject.

Depending on the subject, students may be given tasks of other forms for independent work. What kind of assignments should be given to students is determined by the department. Assignments are carefully designed and aimed at a specific goal, and should serve to strengthen, deepen, expand and complement the knowledge students have acquired during classroom training.

In accordance with the time allocated in the curriculum for student independent work, organizational forms of independent work, assignment options are developed in the relevant departments in each subject and approved by the faculty's educational and methodological council.

Instructions and recommendations are developed for students in each subject to perform independent work, and they are delivered to students in the first session of the subject as a handout.

The main tasks of independent education include:

- a) Deepening and expansion of knowledge;
- b) Formation of interest in creative activity;
- v) Acquisition of educational methods;
- c) Development of understanding and thinking skills;
- d) It includes the formation of the skills of making independent conclusions.

To effectively organize independent education of students:

- a) Systematic approach to organization of all forms of students' independent work;
- b) Coordination and integration of all stages (types) of students' independent work;
- v) Establishing strict control over the quality of students' independent work;
- c) It is desirable to create and improve a mechanism for organizing and controlling students' independent work.

"Today, higher educational institutions in our republic work on the credit-module system. The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies of education and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. In the principle of credit module, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating" [5, 3]

Therefore, the credit-module system consists not only of teaching based on innovative educational technologies, but also of teaching students to learn independently, to have a new attitude to education, to acquire the necessary and deep theoretical knowledge, and to form practical skills based on the demand of the labor market. In short, this system is aimed at the professional development and maturity of the student. It can be said that it is aimed at ensuring the education of a person of knowledge throughout his life and at forming human capital that can meet the labor market and modern requirements. The introduction of the credit-module system is an important factor in the cooperation between the teacher and the student.

In modular education, the pedagogue organizes, manages, advises and checks the student's learning process. And the student moves independently towards the directed object. The greatest emphasis is placed on independent education of students. Development of organizational skills of students in the process of independent education of higher education institutions is one of the main issues

Based on the above-mentioned points, it can be said that it is necessary to establish systematic work in the implementation of the independent education process in higher education institutions, to teach students to work independently, to be creative and socially active, to find their place independently in social and political life, to set promising tasks and to solve problems. will be the basis for forming a new generation of personnel with the ability to do. High-quality communication between the teacher and the student in the process of independent work, the role and importance of the teacher in the process of independent work of students, management functions, modern forms of independent work of students using information and communication technologies, mobile technologies - as a pedagogical problem.

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